

***Cynoglossum zeylanicum* Lehm modulate the expression of the growth factor VEGF-C evidenced by functional obstruction of steroid receptor in early gestation in mice.**

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Abstract: *Cynoglossum zeylanicum* Lehm. is a shrub under the family Boraginaceae found in the Eastern Himalayas' low altitudinal zone. As a traditional remedy for avoiding illnesses, the plant is well-established in the indigenous medical system to regulate women's reproductive performance as per the oral literature. In this present research work, crude root bark extract (CRBE) of *Cynoglossum zeylanicum* has been orally administered along with ovarian steroid antagonist subcutaneously to the experimental animals under laboratory condition. The in-situ localization of VEGF-C in uterine tissues and at the fetal-maternal interface has been accomplished using the technique immunofluorescence and western blot. The expression of VEGF-C has been found strong in the luminal epithelium, stromal cells and decidual cells of the PDZ, SDZ, EPC on D5 to D7 of gestational period of mice. A remarkable transformation of stromal cells into decidual cell has been observed. PDZ that surround the implanting blastocyst starts to proliferate and differentiate into decidual cells (decidualization) and intense expression of VEGF-C has been observed in CRBE treated group. The Decidual Cell Reaction has been observed in CRBE and steroid antagonist co treated group. The mechanism of action of the plant's effect on female reproduction regulation in terms of uterine function modulation. The CRBE exert endometrial proliferation and prepare the LE for embryo reception. The present research work focused on the modulatory effects of CRBE on ovarian steroids and regulate and/or modulate embryo implantation via VEGF-C expression in both the embryo and maternal tissue and transcend its effect in periimplantation period.

Key words: *Cynoglossum zeylanicum*, VEGF-C, decidualization, Immunofluorescence, western blot.